

TRANSVERSE LOADING OF JOINTS IN CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Abhay Raj Singh Gautam and Uday K.Vaidya[®]
Department of Materials Science & Engineering
The University of Alabama at Birmingham
Birmingham, Alabama, USA
[®] *Corresponding author*

Mahesh V. Hosur
Tuskegee University
Center for Advanced Materials
Tuskegee, Alabama, USA

Piyush K. Dutta
U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory
Hanover, New Hampshire, USA

ABSTRACT

Composite structures are finding greater use in military and aerospace applications as structural, load bearing components. The study of bonded joints in structural composites has become an area of interest, as this is the most favorable method of joining composites, and possibly the 'weakest link' in the structure. Composite structures are prone to impact loading such as from bullets, fragments, or flying debris. The present work investigates the effect of transverse loading of adhesive joints with carbon/epoxy composite adherends. The adherends, prepared through Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM), were used to prepare joints with three different adhesive systems. Resin 8604 epoxy, nanoclay reinforced epoxy and a paste adhesive Magnabond 6398. Finite Element Modeling (FEM) of the failure of adhesively bonded joints under transverse impact loading condition was carried out using LS-DYNA 3D software.

KEYWORDS: Adhesive Joints, Transverse Impact, Failure

INTRODUCTION

Considerable amount of work has been done in the design and analysis of adhesive joints. Most of the effort in this area has been to study the in-plane loading behavior of these joints. Various analytical [1-3] and numerical [4-6] models have been proposed to predict the stress distribution and failure conditions for adhesive joints. However, there are very limited studies pertaining to out-of-plane loading of joints. The response of bonded joint towards the transverse loading can be expected to be inferior as compared to their in-plane loading. As in the case of transverse loading the deflection in the joint area will have an effect of compounding the peel stresses.

Goland and Reissner [7] first incorporated the effect of bending deflection on the stress distribution in adhesive layer, thus underlying the effect of adherend deflection on the failure of joints. Various researchers further refined the beam on elastic foundation model proposed by Goland and Reissner [7]. Some of these works have shown the effect of adherend deflection on the stress distribution in the adhesive layer, particularly the peel stresses. The peel stresses are usually responsible for the joint failure, which in turn are affected by the out-of-plane displacement of the adherends.

Tong et al. [8] attempted to correlate the effect of out-of-plane adherend displacement on the stress profile in the adhesive. Their model demonstrated the increase in peel stress at the joint ends with increase in displacement. They have proposed a simple formula to correlate the peel stress in terms of displacement. However, this model is applicable only to in-plane loading of the joint structure where the adherend deflection involved is comparatively small.

Taheri [9] has shown that for the case of epoxy-based adhesives the various stress conditions coupled with the brittle nature of epoxy often causes brittle fracture in the adhesive. However in his work, it was demonstrated that addition of insignificant amount of particulates of SiC (1%) significantly improved the shear and impact response of the adhesive.

EXPERIMENTAL

The composites used for the joints were prepared from plain weave, 6K, 0.43 mm thickness. carbon fabrics with Resinfusion 8604 epoxy matrix. The adhesives identified for joining were Resinfusion 8604 Epoxy, Magnabond 6398 (supplier Magnolia Plastics Inc.), and Reinforced Resinfusion 8604 Epoxy: The epoxy was mixed with 7% (by wt.) nanomer I.30E (supplier Nanocor Inc.), an onium ion surface modified montmorillonite mineral. The mixing of particles was carried out as per the recommendation [10] of the supplier. After proper mixing of particles the epoxy was subjected to vacuum evacuate air bubbles generated during mixing process. Before the process it was made sure that agglomeration or settling of particles didn't take place.

Carbon/epoxy composite panels were fabricated using eight layers of woven carbon fabric. The composite was prepared through VARTM. The composite panels prepared are 3.0 ± 0.1 mm in thickness. The composite panels prepared using VARTM had two types of surface finish. The tool side surface had a mirror finish, while the other side was comparatively rough due to the distribution mesh adjacent to it. This side was used as bonding surface.

Figure1. Schematic of LVI testing of the Joint.

Limited work has been done in testing the transverse impact strength of bonded composite joints. In the present work low velocity impact (LVI) testing of the joints was carried out using an instrumented low velocity impact testing equipment. The schematic of the test setup is shown in Fig. 1. An Instron 8250-Drop Weight Impact Testing Machine equipped with Dynatup 930I-data acquisition system and a pneumatic clamping fixture was used to conduct the tests. Changing the height of impactor varied the impact velocity.

As the tup is released, two velocity sensors record the time of flight. The force transducer is attached to the tip of the tup. A force-time and energy-time response is generated during the test. In case the impactor rebounds there is pneumatic controlled rebound arrestor, which gets actuated after the first impact to prevent multiple impacts.

Tests were carried out with specimen dimension of 150 mm between the clamps with overlap length of 25 mm and width of 25 mm. The ends of the test specimen were rigidly fixed. The specimen was then subjected to impact at various velocities by varying the height of the impactor. The mass of the impactor was 3.33 kg.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The modeling of the behavior of joints under transverse LVI loading was carried out using LS-DYNA 3D software. The experimental results of the LVI tests were used to verify the model. The present approach

Table 1. Material property of composite

Property	Adherends
E_{11} (MPa)	50000
E_{22} (MPa)	50000
E_{33} (MPa)	7200
ν_{12}	0.3
ν_{13}	0.25
ν_{23}	0.25
G_{12} (MPa)	5000
G_{13} (MPa)	3000
G_{23} (MPa)	3000

Table 2. Material properties of adhesive

Property	Neat Epoxy	Magna Bond	Reinforced Epoxy
E (MPa)	2800	2000	3400
ν	0.35	0.35	0.35
γ_{uts} (%)	1.8	3	1.2

for modeling the joint involves the joint configuration and meshing scheme as shown in Fig. 2. The material properties used for the purpose are given in Table 1 and 2. The element type is an 8-noded solid element for both adherend as well as the adhesive. The material behavior of the adherend was simulated using an orthotropic elastic model while the adhesive by plastic kinematic with failure criterion based on maximum strain to failure. Also the model presently doesn't take into consideration any failure at the interface. Hence, the common nodes at the interface are merged together, and the failure is contained in the adhesive layer.

The impactor is modeled as a hemisphere with a mass of 3.333 kg (same as total mass of the impactor in the actual LVI test) using solid 8-node elements and a rigid material type. The point of contact/impact between adherend and impactor was at the center of the joint area. The support condition considered was a fixed-fixed type. All the degrees of freedom were constrained at either end of the adherend. CONTACT_AUTOMATIC_NODE_TO_SURFACE was used to avoid the penetration of impactor into the adherend structure. The impactor is then given an initial velocity and

the result of the simulation is then analyzed in terms of the change in impactor energy and force. In the present analysis, all the reported simulation results were carried out for the initial velocity of 1 m/s imparted in negative z-direction.

Figure 2. Meshing scheme used for simulating impact condition in LS-DYNA

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the LVI testing are shown below in Fig. 3. The plots show the Force and Absorbed Energy vs. Time variation. For the case of neat epoxy the impact velocity was 0.93 m/s and total energy absorbed was 1.2 Joule. The average load at failure was observed to be 0.36 kN. Similarly for the Magnabond paste adhesive and nanoclay reinforced epoxy, the impact velocity was 0.94 m/s and 0.95 m/s respectively. The total energy absorbed was 1.35 J and 1.2 J while peak load at failure was 0.43 kN and 0.45 kN respectively. As can be seen, the total energy absorbed by neat epoxy as well as the nanoclay

modified epoxy is equal. However, the maximum load for failure of the joint was higher for nanoclay

Figure 3. Force applied by the impactor and energy absorbed by the joint Vs time plot for (a) neat epoxy (b) Magnabond and (c) nanoclay reinforced epoxy

modified epoxy than that of the neat epoxy.

It may also be observed that the bulk mechanical property of the epoxy due to addition of nanoclay was affected in various ways. While the elastic modulus of the epoxy increases with the reinforcement, the strain to failure was found to be lower than that of the neat epoxy. In the given loading condition, the joint undergoes considerable deflection, and so does the adhesive. Decrease in the strain to failure has an adverse effect on the load bearing capacity of the joint as can be seen in case of Magnabond adhesive. It has lower elastic modulus but higher strain to failure which requires higher energy for failure as compared to the other two systems.

For the purpose of comparing the measured quantities in the LVI test with those obtained from the FEM model, the 'acceleration times mass' of the impactor was considered to be the resisting force experienced by the impactor. Also the change in the kinetic energy (KE) of the impactor was taken as the energy absorbed by the structure. The results obtained from the model are shown in Fig. 4. The total energy to failure of the joint for the case of neat epoxy, Magnabond and nanoclay reinforced epoxy was found to be 1.25 J, 1.48 J, and 1.14 J respectively, which is in close agreement with the experimental values of 1.2 J, 1.35 J, and 1.2J.

The stress profile from the FEM model showed that the peel as well as the shear stresses peaked along the joint edges as in case of in-plane loading. However, the nature of the peel stress (fig. 4) was tensile near the edge of lower adherend while that along the upper adherend edge was compressive in nature. The magnitude of maximum peel stress was observed to be equivalent to that of the maximum shear stress before the crack initiation. The crack always initiated from the edge with the tensile peel stress. This was observed for both the LVI test as well as the FEM model.

From this it can be inferred that the crack initiation during the transverse loading of the joint takes place under mixed mode condition. However, as the crack propagates, the magnitude of peel stresses at the crack tip is reduced because of the opening of the joint. This constrains the adherends from deflecting freely. However, the magnitude of the compressive stresses on the far end of joint increases to an extent even after the crack starts propagating. At the same time the peak shear stress remains more or less of the same order. As the crack propagates, the state of stress at the crack tip changes from mixed mode to predominantly shear. This was also confirmed by observing the fracture surface of the adhesive after impact. The edge under compressive stresses exhibits shear fracture of the adhesive compared to the rest of the adhesive.

SUMMARY

The transverse impact test of the single lap adhesive joints was conducted. The FEM model developed using finite element code LS-DYNA correlates well with the LVI test results. The important observations can be summarized as:

- The peel stress distribution for transverse loading changes from tensile to compressive stresses.
- The crack always initiates from the edge of the joint where the peel stresses are tensile in nature. However, the failure begins under mixed modes I and II.
- Once the failure initiates, the stress distribution at the crack tip becomes increasingly shear dominated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Support from the U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. L. J. Hart-Smith, NASA Langley Contract Report NASA CR-2218 1973.
2. M. Y. Tsai, J. Morton, "An Evaluation of Analytical and Numerical Solutions to the Single Lap Joint", *Int. J Solids and Structures*, 31, 2537-2563 (1994).
3. M. Y Tsai., D. W. Oplinger, J. Morton, "Improved Theoretical solutions for Adhesive Lap Joints", *Int. J Solids and Structures*, 35, 1163-1185 (1998).
4. C. C. Lin, Y. S. Lin, "A Finite Element Model of Single Lap Joints", *Int. J Solids and Structures*, 30, 1679-1692 (1993).
5. P. C. Pandey, S. Narasimhan, "Three Dimensional Nonlinear Analysis of Adhesively Bonded Lap Joints Considering Viscoplasticity in Adhesives", *Computers and Structures*, 79, 769-783 (2001).
6. D. W. Oplinger, "Effects of Adherend Deflections in Single Lap Joints", *Int. J Solids and Structures*, 31, 2565-2587 (1994).
7. M. Goland, E. Reissner, "Stress in Cemented Joints", *ASME J. Appl. Mech.*, 11, A17-A27 (1944).
8. L. Tong, A. Sheppard, D. Kelly, "Relationship Between Surface Displacement and Adhesive Peel Stress in Bonded Double lap Joints", *Int. J Adhesion and Adhesives*, 15, 43-48 (1995).
9. F. Taheri, "Improvement of Strength and Ductility of Adhesively Bonded joints by Inclusion of SiC Whiskers", *J. Composites Technology & Research JCTRER*, 19, 86-92 (1997).
10. http://www.nanocor.com/tech_sheets/T13%20-%20I30E.pdf